

**Microbiological sampling
and analyses in the food
business operators' HACCP-
based self-control
programmes**

**JIP04- OH-HARMONY-CAP
WP2-T5**

Responsible Partner:

Contributing partners:

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.5																					
Project Acronym	OH-HARMONY-CAP																					
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Due month of the report	Month 50																					
Actual submission month	Month 51																					
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date:																					
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):																					
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other stakeholder(s):.....</td> <td></td> <td>international</td> </tr> </table>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>		National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>			EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Other stakeholder(s):.....		international
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TECHNICAL REPORT: SURVEY OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL SAMPLING AND ANALYSES IN THE FOOD BUSINESS OPERATORS' HACCP-BASED SELF-CONTROL PROGRAMMES

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Integrative Project, Integrative Action-2.2, OH-HARMONY-CAP: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants.

<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

OH-HARMONY-CAP is a project which aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, adaptabilities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly contribute to close the gaps and support future studies on how best to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across One Health sectors. OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium comprises 18 One Health EJP partners across 14 different EU/EEA countries.

1. Summary

The OH-HARMONY-CAP project aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, adaptabilities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory and the primary diagnostic level, focusing on a set of microbial foodborne hazards. For this purpose, a survey aimed to provide an overview of the current procedures for microbiological sampling and analyses among food business operators' Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP)-based self-control programmes in the European Union (EU), was developed within the project and conducted for the first time in EU/ European Economic Area (EEA) countries. It focused on regulated and non-regulated microorganisms, namely six bacteria: *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp.; and five genera/species of parasites: *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*, *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*. Participating EU/EEA countries distributed an online questionnaire to food business operators' laboratories within their countries; and overall, responses from nine EU/EEA countries were received and feedback from 35 laboratories were considered for data analysis. The results reported that dairy products were analysed most frequently and the majority of laboratories analysed both ready-to-eat and non-ready-to-eat products. Accreditation for ISO-standards or an alternative method, was in place in a considerable proportion of the laboratories, but did not cover all the microorganisms selected in this survey. Sending isolates for further confirmation to external laboratories was common for laboratories analysing bacteria and *Cryptosporidium* spp. In contrast, storing isolates was less frequently established. Around 60% of laboratories used more than one typing or characterisation method, predominantly MALDI-TOF, antimicrobial resistance typing and PCR, while 40% did not type nor characterise the isolates of the microorganisms detected. Variability was also observed regarding use of Whole Genome Sequencing; and participation in external quality assessments or in Proficiency Tests programmes. A low proportion of laboratories mainly analysed the targeted microorganisms included in this survey, representing 61 to 100% of their total workload. The study gathered insight into current microbiological sampling and analyses in food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes. Further efforts are needed to harmonise sampling and analytical protocols among these laboratories to gain better insight into the prevalence of foodborne pathogens and related risks of transmission.

2. Introduction

The OH-HARMONY-CAP project aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, adaptabilities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The project focuses on a set of microbial foodborne hazards: Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* spp. and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp.

The aim of Work Package 2 (WP2) within the project is to establish an OHLabCap instrument that is generic, adjustable and sustainable at both an EU/EEA and national level, that should support harmonised data collection and validation, and encourage cross-sectoral communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthening national networks. This requires identifying and characterising One Health laboratory interoperability, capacity and performance in each step within the system (e.g. coordination, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and dissemination of data). This integrative approach will be performed by conducting surveys aimed at NRL and primary diagnostic level.

To achieve the WP2 objective, a survey aimed to provide an overview of the current procedures for microbiological sampling and analyses in food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes, was developed and conducted for the first time in EU/EEA countries. The rationale for this survey was that similar investigations are conducted in the framework of national monitoring

programmes or as part of official investigations, that include food sampling and laboratory testing by competent authorities. However, the results obtained in these investigations differ largely from the results derived from food business operators' self-control programmes. Gaining this insight could improve the evaluation of their results and further scientific interpretations, not only at a national level but in an European context.

A questionnaire focused on six priority bacteria: *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp.; and five priority parasites: *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*, *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*, was developed from February to April 2021, and distributed from May to July 2021 in the participating EU/EEA countries.

The responses provided information on the food categories or the food areas that were examined, the implementation of ISO-standards and laboratory accreditation, whether laboratories sent their isolates for external analysis or not, the length of storage of isolates, the typing or characterisation methods used for each microorganism, and the participation in external quality assessments or Proficiency Testing programmes (see Appendix 1 for the content of the full survey).

It was an important data collection exercise to describe the One Health microbiological sampling system by surveying food laboratories across participating EU/EEA countries. The information collected will be used to identify gaps and needs necessary to develop and implement harmonised and compatible protocols for the detection and typing of foodborne pathogens across One Health sectors.

3. Results

3.1 Participation in the survey

Laboratories from nine EU/EEA countries (Sweden, The Netherlands, Portugal, Germany, Finland, Norway, Denmark, France, Estonia) participated in the survey, obtaining an overall of 44 respondent laboratories. From these, 35 responses came from microbiological laboratories working with one or more of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites; these were included in the analysis (Table 1). The majority of laboratories analysed samples for more than one of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites (Table 2).

Table 1. Survey participants

EU/EEA countries	N° of respondent laboratories	N° of laboratories considered in the analysis
Sweden	11	3
The Netherlands	8	8
Portugal	8	8
Germany	5	4
Finland	4	4
Norway	3	3
Denmark	2	2
France	2	2
Estonia	1	1
Total	44	35

Table 2. Laboratories per bacteria or parasite

Bacteria	N° of laboratories
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	31
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	28
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	16
Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	9
<i>Shigella</i> spp.	9
<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	7
Parasites	
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	7
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	3
<i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (sensu lato)	2
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	2
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	1

3.2 Food categories and food areas

The food categories and food areas considered in the survey were the following: dairy products, fish and seafood, meat and products thereof, vegetables, fruits and products thereof, bakery products, egg products, beverages, ready-to-eat mixed meals, and food processing area and environmental surfaces. A minimum of 14 and a maximum of 29 microbiological laboratories analysed samples in each food category or food area (Figure 1). The food category beverages was the category analysed by the lowest number of laboratories participating in the survey, whereas dairy products was the food category analysed by the highest proportion (82.9%) of laboratories.

The majority (62.9%) of laboratories investigated food samples from both ready-to-eat and non-ready-to-eat products.

Figure 1. Food categories and food areas analysed by the laboratories.

3.3 Implementation of ISO-standards in laboratories

Respectively, 77.1% and 74.3% of laboratories analysing the six priority bacteria and the five priority parasites had ISO-standards or an alternative method implemented (Figure 2). Examples of alternative methods included national standards, such as the DIN standards for Germany, and validated alternative methods certified by organizations such as AFNOR, MicroVal, NordVal or others.

Figure 2. Laboratories with ISO-standards or an alternative method implemented

3.3.1 Accreditation among laboratories

The majority of laboratories with ISO-standards implemented (68.6%) were accredited; except laboratories analysing *Trichinella* spp. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Accredited laboratories with ISO-standards

The majority of laboratories with an alternative method implemented (62.9%), were accredited; except laboratories analysing *Campylobacter spp.*, Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella spp.*, *Yersinia spp.* and *Cryptosporidium spp.* (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Accredited laboratories with an alternative method

3.4 Proportion of laboratories which sent out isolates for external analyses

A total of 12% of laboratories analysing the six priority bacteria sent their isolates to other laboratories for external analyses (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Laboratories which sent out their isolates for external analyses.

3.5 Proportion of laboratories which stored isolates

A total of 52% of laboratories analysing the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites did not store their isolates. Among the laboratories, 49% of laboratories analysing the six priority bacteria and 54% of laboratories analysing the five priority parasites, did not store isolates (Figure 6). The laboratories which stored their isolates, typically stored them for longer than one year.

Figure 6. Laboratories which stored their isolates and length of storage

3.6 Typing and characterisation methods

Altogether, 60% of laboratories reported using more than one typing or characterisation method, predominantly MALDI-TOF, antimicrobial resistance typing and PCR/RT-PCR, while the rest 40% did not type nor characterise. Laboratories analysing the six priority bacteria used a wider variety of typing and characterisation methods than the laboratories analysing the five priority parasites. A total of 17.1% of laboratories reported using Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Typing and characterisation methods reported by the laboratories

3.7 Participation in External Quality Assessments (EQAs) or Proficiency Testing programmes (PT)

The majority of laboratories participated in EQAs or PT; although, four, seven and four of the laboratories analysing Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp., respectively, did not participate in EQAs nor PT (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Participation of laboratories in EQAs or PT

3.8 Laboratories' workload represented by the analyses of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites

Fifteen laboratories analysed other microorganisms than the targeted six priority bacteria and five priority parasites. In these laboratories, the analysis of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites included in the survey represented $\leq 30\%$ of their workload (Figure 9).

Six laboratories mainly analysed the targeted six priority bacteria and five priority parasites, representing 61 to 100% of their workload.

Figure 9. Laboratories' workload represented by the analyses of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites

4. Conclusions

- The data collected in this survey provided an overview of the current procedures for microbiological sampling and analyses performed by the food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes in EU/EEA countries.
- The reasons underlying the relatively small turnout should be interpreted cautiously. Partly it may be due to the fact that the survey was sent out during the summer season, and partly due to many laboratories were private and could not prioritise their participation in the survey. On the other hand, the reduced participation could also be explained by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdown measures adopted during 2020 still with repercussions during 2021.
- Only the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites were included in the survey. If other pathogens had been included, probably more laboratories would have participated providing more information on the analyses performed within the food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes.
- Half of the respondent laboratories reported storing their isolates, which may reflect lack of awareness on the importance of storing the strains for further studies. Some laboratories may have insufficient storage capacity and, moreover, storing of isolates demands further costs. In order to send the isolates to a reference laboratory for further analyses or to be able to characterise and type the isolate later, it is important that laboratories improve their procedures and storage capacity and conditions.
- WGS-based typing was performed by a third of laboratories that reported using typing and characterisation methods, representing 17.1% of respondent laboratories. WGS based typing is available to respond to hazard characterisation questions, and is quickly changing the surveillance approach specially for foodborne bacterial agents. The routine application of WGS is, however, hindered by the availability of the technology as well as by the lack of harmonisation for data analysis and concerns on the legal aspects associated with the collection of genomic data. Although the cost for WGS-based typing has decreased in recent years, it may still be too high to include WGS-based typing in all the routine analyses.
- The majority of the responding laboratories participated in External Quality Assessments or Proficiency Testing programmes, which are mandatory for accreditation and an important tool to monitor the quality of the laboratory performance through comparisons with other laboratories. However, a substantial proportion of laboratories analysing Shiga toxin-producing

E. coli (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp., did not participate in any External Quality Assessments nor Proficiency Testing programmes.

5. Recommendations

Further efforts are needed to obtain reliable data that could be used to harmonise sampling and analytical protocols among laboratories for a better insight into the prevalence of foodborne pathogens and related risks.

6. Acknowledgement

We would like to acknowledge all the laboratories participating in the present survey.

This survey was supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme.

7. Appendix

Survey's questionnaire

Survey targeting the HACCP-based self-control programs

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Dear Colleague,

OH-Harmony-CAP aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, adaptability, and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. This project will provide a description of the One Health (OH) microbiology system by surveying food, feed and veterinary OH laboratories across all EU/EEA countries. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and suggest future studies of how best to detect and characterise food borne pathogens across the One Health sectors.

The project will collect information on six priority bacteria and five priority parasites:

1. *Campylobacter* spp.
 2. *Listeria monocytogenes*
 3. *Salmonella* spp.
 4. Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
 5. *Shigella* spp.
 6. *Yersinia* spp.
-
1. *Cryptosporidium* spp.
 2. *Echinococcus granulosus* (*sensu lato*)
 3. *Echinococcus multilocularis*
 4. *Toxoplasma gondii*
 5. *Trichinella* spp.

To provide an overview, of the sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs, the OH-Harmony-CAP project has included this optional online survey. Due to the lack of knowledge and overview of how many samples that are taken and processed by the food business operators and examined for microorganism, we would appreciate your contribution by filling in this survey focused on public health relevant microorganism.

Note, participation in this survey is anonymous. The information gathered will be included in a technical report and the results of this survey will be open source data and will be published on <https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>.

For more information on the OH-Harmony-cap project please visit our website <https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

Thank you for your contribution!

Catarina Flink and Monica Ricão Canelhas
Swedish Food Agency
And
Nadia Boisen and Flemming Scheutz
OH-Harmony-Cap Coordinators

Instructions for filling out the survey

Due to the wide scope of questions, the survey may require more than one person to fill out the survey. If needed, the survey can at any point be saved and shared between colleagues so that the responsible person(s) for each of the priority bacteria and parasites can fill out their part.

1. If you need to share the survey link with your colleagues, follow the steps as described in the invitation email
2. Fill out the survey on the basis of your laboratory and/or institute
3. Data from research projects should not be included
4. The average time to fill out the survey is 15 minutes (time to collect data for the answers not included).

Survey on the microbiological analyses within the HACCP-based self-control programs

Note, please answer the following questions on the basis of what is being processes and analysed only in your laboratory

- * 1. Select the food category/food area of the samples analyzed in your laboratory. If applicable, select more than one option

- Dairy products
- Fish and seafood
- Meat and products thereof
- Vegetable and fruits and products thereof
- Bakery products
- Egg products
- Beverages
- Ready-to-eat mixed meals
- Food processing area, environmental surfaces
- Other processed food and prepared dishes
- Broiler carcasses
- Pig carcasses
- Cattle carcasses
- Other

1a. Please indicate if category/food is Ready-to-eat or Non Ready-to-eat

	Ready-to-eat	Non Ready-to-eat
* Dairy products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Fish and seafood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Meat and products thereof	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Vegetable and fruits and products thereof	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Bakery products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Egg products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 2 . Which of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites does your laboratory analyse?
(Please, check more than one box)

- Campylobacter* spp.
- Listeria monocytogenes*
- Salmonella* spp.
- Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC)
- Shigella* spp.
- Yersinia* spp.
- Cryptosporidium* spp.
- Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*
- Echinococcus multilocularis*
- Toxoplasma gondii*
- Trichinella* spp.
- None of the above

2a. How many samples did your laboratory analyze (mean of the last 3 years: 2018, 2019, 2020)?

Note, please do not include typing

Note, If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA"

	Number of samples (mean of the last 3 years)
• <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
• <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
• <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
• Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	
• <i>Shigella</i> spp.	
• <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	
• <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
• <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
• <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
• <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
• <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

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2b. How many positive samples did your laboratory analyse (mean of the last 3 years: 2018, 2019, 2020)?

Note, please do not include typing

Note, If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA"

	Number of samples (mean of the last 3 years)
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	
<i>Shigella</i> spp.	
<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
<i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

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3. Does your laboratory use ISO standards for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites (typing not included)?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3a. If yes, is your laboratory accredited for the utilised ISO standard (typing not included)?

	Accreditation, yes	Accreditation, no	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Does your laboratory use alternative methods for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites (typing not included)?

	Yes	No	NA

* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4a. If yes, is your laboratory accredited for that method (typing not included)?

	Accreditation, yes	Accreditation, no	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4b. Please specify the alternative method your laboratory is using for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites (typing not included).

Note, If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA"

	Alternative method
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	

<i>Shigella</i> spp.	
<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
<i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

5. Do you send out any of the six priority pathogens and five priority parasites for external analysis?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. In case of positive samples, from which of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites does your laboratory store?

	Storing	No storing	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6a. How long does your laboratory store the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

	< Six months	Six months	One year	> One year
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Does your laboratory characterize/type the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites *i.e.* molecular, microscopy, sero- and/or biochemically

- Yes
- Occasionally
- No

7a. Which methods does your laboratory use for typing of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?
 (If needed, please check more than one answer)

	Antibiotic typing	Microscopy	Serotyping	PFGE	MLVA	PCR /RT-PCR	MLST	MALDI-TOF	WGS	Other	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										

PFGE: Pulsed-Field Gel Electrophoresis
 MLVA: Multilocus Variable number tandem repeat Analysis
 PCR/RT-PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction/Real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction
 MLST: Multilocus Sequence Typing
 MALDI-TOF: Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight
 WGS: Whole Genome Sequencing

* 8. Does your laboratory participate in external quality assessments/proficiency tests?

- Yes
- No

8a. For which of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites, does your laboratory take part in external quality assessments or proficiency tests?

	Quality assessments	Proficiency tests	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 9. Which proportion of the total work carried out in your laboratory represents the analysis of these microorganisms?

- ≤ 30%
- 31-60%
- 61-80%
- 81-100%

Contact information

Note, any identifiable information will not appear in the final report

Name of laboratory
(Not mandatory)

* Country

Email address
(Not mandatory)

Final Comments

Is there anything else you wish to add to the information you have provided?

Acknowledgement

Thank you for your participation!

The Harmony project is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement Number 773830.

<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

